

Aluminium chloride assisted zinc-induced reduction of some α,β -unsaturated ketones

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Abstract : Some α,β -unsaturated ketones are reduced to give cyclodimerization products and/or β,β -coupling products in presence of $\text{Zn}\cdot\text{AlCl}_3\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ -moist THF and aluminium chloride acts as Lewis acid to increase the yield of the products.

Keywords : α,β -Unsaturated ketones, reduction, aluminium chloride, zinc.

Introduction

Syntheses of organic compounds using environmentally benign reagents under mild conditions have lately been receiving much attention from organic chemists. Experimentally simple methodology, easy separation techniques and use of cheap/readily available reagents are still interesting and important in organic synthesis. Recently, a number of publications and reviews¹⁻¹⁰ have advocated the use of metal-mediated organic synthesis. Ytterbium was the first metal to promote the cyclodimerization¹¹ of α,β -unsaturated ketones. Zhou *et al.* reported the same by reduction of low valent titanium¹². Formation of novel reductive cyclodimerization products **2** along with β,β -coupling products **3** from α,β -unsaturated ketones **1a-c** using $\text{Zn}/\text{THF}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have recently been reported¹³ by Dey *et al.* But, the fact was that the yields of both the types of products were not good. Attempts were made to improve the yield of the products formed by $\text{Zn}/\text{THF}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ reduction. The mole ratio of the starting materials and Zn-dust was varied to see the out come of the product but, there were no significant improvement in the yield of the said products. Attempts were also made to apply this simple technique for reduction of **1d-h** (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

It is important to note that starting material **1d-g** afforded only β,β -coupling product under the same reduction condition but, the starting material **1h** did not give any kind of above mentioned products. However, as there was no significant improvement in the yield of the said reduction products by varying the mole ratio of the starting materials and Zn-dust, so author intended to modify the method.

In this endeavor, author used $\text{Zn}\cdot\text{AlCl}_3\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ -moist THF for reduction of **1a-h** and it was found that the yield of the products were increased by 8–14% almost in each case under this modified condition. It was also observed that the said reaction was faster than that of $\text{Zn}/\text{THF}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ method. All the starting materials gave same products in each case as obtained by $\text{Zn}/\text{THF}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ method¹³.

Results and discussion

It is known to us that aliphatic aldehydes and ketones, aromatic ketones, and esters are un-reactive, while typical aromatic aldehydes, α,β -unsaturated aldehydes, and some α,β -unsaturated ketones undergo one electron reduction with formation of bimolecular products¹⁴⁻¹⁶. Initially, chalcones **1a-c** were subjected for reduction under $\text{Zn}/\text{THF}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ reduction condition by varying the mole ratio of the starting materials and Zn-dust but, there were no significant improvement in the yield of the products. To evaluate the scope of the $\text{Zn}/\text{THF}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ reduction method (Method-I) compounds **1d-h** were subjected and in case of **1d-g** only β,β -coupling products were formed. Compound **1h** did not response to this reduction procedure. To improve the yield of the products **1a-g** were

reduced with Zn-AlCl₃.6H₂O-moist THF (Method-II) at room temperature. All the starting materials **1a-g** gave same products like Zn/THF.H₂O reduction method. Compound **1h** also did not give any product under this modified condition. The yields of the products were increased by 8–14% (Table 1) almost in each case under Zn-AlCl₃.6H₂O-moist THF reduction condition.

radical from α,β -unsaturated ketones and hence stabilization too. The first step of the reaction corresponds to a rapid equilibrium between starting material and aluminium chloride. The electron transfer occurs in the rate determining step to give both the types of products. From the mechanistic pathway, it is evident that the spin electron density may be highest either at position 2 or at position

Table 1. Aluminium chloride assisted Zn-induced reduction of some α,β -unsaturated ketones

Starting material	Product(s) (yield %)	
	Method-I	Method-II
1a : R = R' = Ph	2a (31) + 3a (11)	2a (40) + 3a (20)
1b : R = <i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₅ , R' = Ph	2b (34) + 3b (17)	2b (44) + 3b (26)
1c : R = 3,4-OCH ₂ OC ₆ H ₃ , R' = Ph	2c (35) + 3c (14)	2c (45) + 3c (24)
1d : R = Ph, R' = <i>o</i> -HOC ₆ H ₄	3d (30)	3d (39)
1e : R = <i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ , R' = <i>o</i> -HOC ₆ H ₄	3e (27)	3e (37)
1f : R = <i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ , R' = CH ₃	3f (28)	3f (40)
1g : <i>E</i> -3-(Furfurylidene)flavanone	3g (31)	3g (42)
1h : <i>E</i> -3-(4-Methoxybenzylidene)flavanone	No product	No product

The increase in yield of the products under the modified condition may be explained considering the role of AlCl₃ as Lewis acid (Scheme 2) during the course of the reaction.

Scheme 2

The co-ordination of the lone pair of oxygen atom of the carbonyl group in the starting material with the vacant *p*-orbital of Al in AlCl₃ facilitates the generation of

4 depending on the stability of the radical species resulted during the course of the reaction. As no diol was obtained in any case, so it is obvious that the spin electron density is highest at position 4, not at position 2 of the radical anion complex. Formation of only β,β -coupling products comparatively in greater yield for compounds **1d-g** may be due to greater spin electron density at position 4 of the radical anion complex. Melting point and spectral data of the products **2a-c** and **3a-c** were the same as reported¹¹⁻¹³.

In conclusion, a simple efficient and environmentally friendly methodology has been developed to increase the yield of the cyclodimerization products and/or β,β -coupling products using milder reagents and shortening the time for reduction of some α,β -unsaturated ketones.

The spectral data of the products **3d-g** are given below :

Compound **3d** : C₃₀H₂₆O₄, m.p. 111–113 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3280 (O–H), 1682 (C=O); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.40 (4H, d, *J* 6.0 Hz, H₄- α), 3.86 (2H, br t, *J* 6.0 Hz, H₂- β), 6.83–6.98 (8H, m, Ar-H), 7.16–7.23 (6H, m, Ar-H), 7.40–7.46 (2H, dt, *J* 7.0 and 1.5 Hz, H₂-4'), 7.65 (1H, dd, *J* 8.1 and 1.5 Hz, H₂-6') and 12.14 (2H, exchangeable with D₂O, O–H).

Compound **3e**: $C_{32}H_{30}O_6$, m.p. 170–171 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr): 3340 (O–H), 1685 (C=O); 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$): δ 2.91 (2H, dd, J 16.0 and 2.1 Hz, $H_{2A-\alpha}$), 3.09–3.18 (2H, m, $H_{2B-\alpha}$), 3.52 (2H, br t, J 7.5 and 3.3 Hz, $H_2-\beta$), 3.68 (6H, s, $2 \times OCH_3$), 6.68–6.80 (8H, m, Ar-H), 7.17–7.20 (6H, m, Ar-H), 7.27–7.32 (2H, dt, J 8.4 and 1.2 Hz, H_2-4'), 7.36–7.39 (1H, dd, J 8.1 and 1.2 Hz, H_2-6'), 12.01 (2H, exchangeable with D_2O , O–H).

Compound **3f**: $C_{20}H_{22}O_6$, m.p. 156–157 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr): 1715 (C=O); 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$): δ 1.69 (6H, s, $2 \times CH_3$), 2.31 (2H, dd, J 16.5 and 3.0 Hz, $H_{2A-\alpha}$), 2.57–2.66 (2H, m, $H_{2B-\alpha}$), 3.32 (2H, br t, J 7.5 and 3.6 Hz, $H_2-\beta$), 7.15–7.32 (10H, m, Ar-H).

Compound **3g**: $C_{40}H_{30}O_6$, m.p. 285–287 °C; IR ν_{\max} (KBr): 1680 (C=O); 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$): δ 3.0 (2H, dt, J 11.4 and 1.2 Hz, H_2-3), 4.34 (2H, d, J 1 Hz, $H_2-\beta$), 4.99 (2H, d, J 11.4 Hz, H_2-2), 5.94 (2H, dd, J 3.6 and 0.6 Hz, H_2-3''), 6.22 (2H, dd, J 3.3 and 1.8 Hz, H_2-4''), 6.63 (2H, d, J 8.1 Hz, H_2-8), 6.92 (2H, dt, J 9.0 and 1.3 Hz, H_2-6), 7.27–7.50 (14H, m, Ar-H) and 7.74 (2H, dd, J 7.8 and 1.5 Hz, H_2-5).

Typical experimental procedure: α,β -Unsaturated ketone (0.01 mol) was added to a well stirred mixture of Zn-dust (0.04 mol), $AlCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ (0.001 mol) and moist THF (12 ml) at room temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred for about 7 h. The resulting reaction mixture was poured into saturated ammonium chloride solution (60 ml) and it was extracted with diethyl ether (3×40 ml). The organic layer was washed with brine (2×40 ml) and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue obtained after removal of solvent was subjected to column chromatograph over silica gel when pure products were obtained.

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